

IPBES VA Chapter 2. Literature review on the diverse perspectives on fisheries at the global scale / IPBES values assessment (2.5)

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Description

This review corresponds to the IPBES values assessment. The review presents a concrete example on how nature's contributions to people are considered in decision-making, while exploring which are the worldviews, knowledge systems, broad and specific values and indicators that are brought into decisions. It also seeks to understand if and how more plural valuation processes can provide relevant input towards transformational change leading to sustainability. The review consisted of a rapid assessment of the extent to which diverse perspectives on fisheries at the global scale are reflected in the scientific literature

and how this has aligned with decision-making tools for management. The cross-cutting topic on fisheries in the global oceans was developed for use between chapters, particularly *chapters 2 and 4*.

Process overview

Protocol

- **Type of review:** Systematic review of publications focused on fisheries, assembled within the context of the High Level Panel for a Sustainable Ocean Economy, established in 2018
- **Search languages:** English
- **Sample extracted:** 142 publications
- **Location and format of the data (A):** IPBES_VA_2.5_012-2020_(A).pdf

Treatment applied: Full text was retrieved for 128 publications (B), while the remainder were unavailable and were excluded from the analysis.

- **Sample extracted:** 128 scientific publications
- **Location and format of the data (B):** IPBES_VA_2.5_26-4-2021_(B).pdf

Treatment applied: The collected sources (B) were analysed and coded using the MaxQDA2020 software, according to the codes shown in (R1). The codes were chosen by all members of the working team for this review and were adjusted based on the findings presented in the second order draft of the chapters and the first order draft of the summary for policy makers of the IPBES values assessment. Only specific parts of each source were coded. In the case of multilateral and non-academic sources, only the executive summaries and conclusions were coded. In scientific papers, the abstract, discussion and conclusion were coded. The number of segments coded for each source can be found in (C).

- **Location and format of the data (C):** IPBES_VA_2.5_31-5-2021_(C).csv

Results of the analysis can be found in annex 2.11. In the annex, figures 2.36 - 2.41 can be backed up by the data found in (D).

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA_2.5_12-2020_(A)	pdf	185 KB	List of 142 scientific publications
B	IPBES_VA_2.5_26-4-2021_(B)	pdf	292 KB	List of 128 scientific publications
C	IPBES_VA_2.5_31-5-2021_(C)	csv	15 KB	Segments coded for each source
D	IPBES_VA_2.5_31-5-2021_(D)	pdf	143 KB	Data backing up figures 2.36-2.41 in annex 2.11
R1	IPBES_VA_2.5_30-4-2021_(R1)	csv	5 KB	Codes used to analyse the 128 scientific publications in (B)